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RELIGION AND ETHNIC POLITICS AMONG THE INDEGINOUS PEOPLE OF USSA L G A. TARABA STATE, NIGERIA.

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ABSTRACT

In Nigeria, ethnicity and religion are deeply intertwined with politics, often leading to tensions and conflicts. The country's diverse ethnic landscape, combined with religious differences, creates fertile ground for political manipulation. This article examined the intersection of religion and ethnicity in the political landscape of Ussa Local Government Area, Taraba State, Nigeria, with a focus on the inherent problems and potential prospects. Using a qualitative approach supported by conflict theory, the study explored how religious and ethnic affiliations have been politicised, contributing to marginalisation, electoral violence, and weakened democratic institutions. The findings revealed that political actors often exploit identity sentiments to gain or retain power, resulting in social divisions and governance inefficiencies. However, the study also identified viable prospects for change, including inclusive governance, interfaith dialogue, and civic education as mechanisms for promoting unity and political stability. The study concluded that while the challenges of religion and ethnic politics in Ussa are significant, they are not insurmountable. With deliberate policy interventions and active community engagement, the LGA can harness its diversity as a tool for sustainable development and peaceful coexistence.

KEYWORDS; Religion, Ethnicity, Politics, Problems, Prospects.

INTRODUCTION

In contemporary Nigeria, despite the formal declaration of the country as a secular state, religion continues to play a profound and visible role in public life. This influence extends beyond the spiritual realm, deeply shaping political, social, and cultural dimensions of society (Ezeibe, Osakwe & Mbah, 2020). Across various regions, religious affiliations significantly affect voting behaviours, policy preferences, and political alliances (Agbo & Idike, 2021). This dynamic is particularly evident in Taraba State, where the socio-political landscape has historically been influenced by complex interactions between religion and politics (Ibrahim et al. 2015).

Ussa Local Government Area (LGA), situated in southern Taraba State, presents a compelling context for examining the interplay between religion and ethnicity in political life. The area is religiously diverse, with Christianity being the predominant faith, while Islam and African Traditional Religion constitute the minority. Each religious group plays a vital role in shaping the socio-political attitudes and behaviours of the community. Religious institutions in Ussa often serve as moral and ethical custodians, influencing public discourse and civic engagement. Religious leaders not only guide spiritual growth but also serve as mediators in communal disputes, promoters of social welfare, and advocates for peace and tolerance. Ekanem and Okon, 2019.

However, the influence of religion in Ussa LGA is not without challenges. In many instances, religious identity has been instrumentalised for political advantage.

Politicians often exploited religious sentiments to consolidate support, gain legitimacy, or marginalise opposing groups. This manipulation fosters division, mistrust, and at times, violent conflict as reported by Ibeanu & Orji, (2016). Inter-religious and inter-ethnic tensions have been reported, particularly during election periods, reflecting a deeper structural problem where religion and politics are entangled in ways that undermine social harmony [Mustapha, 2019].

Furthermore, issues such as the marginalisation of minority ethnic and religious groups persist, often resulting in feelings of exclusion and disenfranchisement. These dynamics as opined by Ezeibe et al., (2020) have the potential to weaken democratic institutions, erode trust in governance, and threaten the peaceful coexistence of the communities and beyond.

Given these concerns, this study seeks to explore the problems and prospects associated with the intersection of religion and ethnic politics in Ussa Local Government Area. By examining how religious and ethnic identities influence political behaviours, leadership selection, policy formulation, and inter-group relations, the research aims to generate insights that can inform conflict management strategies and promote inclusive governance.

BACKGROUND TO THE STUDY

Understanding the relationship between religion and politics in Ussa LGA is crucial for managing diversity, reducing identity-based conflict, and building sustainable

peace in Taraba State. The findings of this study are expected to provide practical recommendations for policymakers, religious leaders, civil society actors, and community members committed to fostering unity and political stability in pluralistic society. The population of Ussa Local Government Area is said to be 92, 017(N.P. C,2006).

- **Religion**

Religion refers to a set of organised beliefs, practices, and systems that connect humanity to spirituality and moral values (Pargament, 2013). In the context of this study, religion encompasses the major religious affiliations in Ussa Local Government Area: Christianity, Islam, and African Traditional Religion, which influence both personal identity and public life. As Tillich (1957) described it, religion is “the state of being grasped by an ultimate concern,” which often shapes societal norms and political behaviours.

Also, Religion, in its broadest sense, is a system of beliefs and practices through which people express their relationship with the sacred, the divine, or ultimate reality. It typically encompasses worship, moral conduct, rituals, and often a narrative that provides meaning to existence. Scholars such as Emile Durkheim viewed religion as a social institution that reinforces group cohesion, while Geertz (1973) defined religion as a cultural system of symbols that shapes human understanding and behaviours . More contemporary perspectives, such as those of Linda Woodhead (2017), recognise the plurality and transformation of religion in the modern world, emphasising its dynamic and evolving nature in response to globalisation, modernity, and political shifts.

Religion is both deeply personal and inherently social. It intersects with politics, identity, economics, and culture, making it a vital subject in the study of human societies. Nowhere is this more evident than in Africa, where traditional beliefs coexist with world religions like Christianity and Islam, often resulting in complex religious landscapes.

- **Ethnicity**

Ethnicity is defined as a social construct that categorises people based on shared cultural traits such as language, ancestry, traditions, and beliefs (Eriksen, 2010). In the context of this study, ethnicity pertains to the diverse cultural groups in Ussa LGA and how their identities intersect with religious and political affiliations.

- **Politics**

Politics is the practice and theory of influencing people on a civic or individual level. Politics is derived from the Greek word "polis," meaning city-state, implying governance. Onyekpe (2003) described politics as the control and exercise of power, Madu (2004) considered it a fundamental aspect of human social existence, while Ejizu (1988) defined it as a dynamic process of managing resources to enforce public policies. The goal of politics, according to political economy experts, is the realisation of the commonwealth. Invariably, politics is essential in managing social order and human interactions. According to Heywood, (2019), it concerns how power and resources are distributed and how decisions are made within a community.

In this study, politics refers specifically to the structures, processes, and activities through which political leadership is sought and

exercised in Ussa Local Government Area, especially as influenced by religious and ethnic affiliations.

- **Problem**

A problem, in this context, denotes a condition or situation that hinders social harmony or effective governance. It includes the challenges arising from the entanglement of religion and ethnicity in political affairs, such as conflict, marginalisation, and distrust within the Ussa Local Government Area (Agbiji & Swart, 2015).

- **Prospect**

Prospect refers to the potential or possibility for positive outcomes or improvements in the future.

In this study, the term explores the opportunities for peaceful coexistence, inclusive governance, and strengthened social cohesion, should religion and ethnicity be managed constructively within Ussa's political sphere (Obiefuna & Uroko, 2019).

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN RELIGION AND POLITICS

The interplay between religion and politics in Nigeria is both historical and contemporary. While modern democracies advocate for secularism, Nigeria experiences significant religious influence in political processes. Religious leaders often act as opinion leaders, influencing political decisions and electoral choices. This interaction can foster social cohesion and political participation, but may also incite division when manipulated. Ohazurike (2023) noted that the intertwining of religion and politics has undermined Nigeria's efforts to build an enduring

multireligious democratic society, leading to political instability and polarisation.

- **The Involvement of Religion in Politics**

Religion has historically played a central role in Nigeria's political affairs. Religious institutions and leaders often shape political discourse, endorse candidates, and mobilise followers. In local contexts like Ussa LGA, religious affiliations can significantly determine voters' behaviours and political appointments. Afolabi (2015) highlights that political office holders often misuse religion as a tool to gain power, while religious leaders may leverage their influence for personal gain.

Christianity, particularly in Southern and parts of the Middle Belt of Nigeria, has been a significant influence in socio-political matters. Churches and Christian organisations have increasingly participated in political advocacy and public policy discussions. In Ussa LGA, where Christianity is predominant, churches play a vital role in influencing political orientations. As Onapajo (2016) observes, during the 2015 presidential elections, Christian leaders and institutions were actively involved in political mobilisation, endorsing candidates and shaping electoral outcomes.

Islam, predominant in Northern Nigeria, significantly influences political behaviours. Islamic leaders, such as Imams and scholars, wield spiritual and temporal authority, shaping political opinions among their followers. While Islam is not the dominant religion in Ussa LGA, its principles and leaders still impact political participation in areas with Muslim populations. Ohazurike

(2023) discussed how the introduction of Islam into Northern Nigeria has led to its domineering influence in the socio-political and economic lives of the people, contributing to inter-religious tensions.

African traditional religion (ATR) represents the indigenous religious practices of African communities. Although often marginalised in political discourse, ATR holds cultural significance in Ussa and similar communities. Traditional rulers as custodians of cultural practices, and often adherents of ATR, play mediating roles in political matters. Onebunne (2018) emphasises that ATR's influence is profound, reinforcing regional and ethnic differences and affecting national stability.

Religion influences politics in various ways, including policy-making, campaign strategies, and governance styles. Religious values often shape leaders' attitudes toward corruption, social justice, and public morality. Political actors use religious rhetoric to legitimise their positions and connect with voters. However, such influence can be both constructive and destructive. Chimaobi and Musa (2024) argue that the manipulation of religious sentiments for political gain often exacerbates divisions, hindering efforts towards national cohesion and inclusive governance.

IMPLICATION OF RELIGIOUS INVOLVEMENT IN POLITICS

The implications of religious involvement in politics are profound. Positively, religion can promote civic engagement and ethical

leadership. Negatively, the politicisation of religion can lead to identity politics and the

exclusion of minority groups. Madami (2023) notes that religion, ethnicity, and politics have hindered national integration in Nigeria, recommending the fostering of a politics, particularly in localised settings like Ussa Local Government Area (LGA).

In Nigeria, politicians frequently exploit religious affiliations to gain legitimacy and discredit opponents. Clerics are sometimes co-opted into political campaigns, and religious rhetorics are employed to sway public opinion (Udoidem & Essien, 2018). In Ussa LGA, political actors may align with dominant religious groups to secure votes and political leverage, often exacerbating existing communal tensions.

This consistently indicates that religion can both unify and divide within the political sphere. Onapajo (2016) notes that while religion played a central role in the pre-election period of the 2015 elections, other factors, especially candidates' profiles and performance records, took precedence over religious and ethnic considerations on election day. However, Agbo et al. (2021) emphasise that the electoral choices of voters during the 2015 presidential election were based on ethnic and religious considerations, leading to unfair distribution of political appointments and infrastructural projects, which have deepened and sustained ethno-regional agitations. These studies highlight the need for inclusive political frameworks that transcend religious and ethnic divisions, a consideration that is particularly pertinent for local governance in areas like Ussa LGA. (Udoidem & Essien, 2018).

While substantial research exists on the intersection of religion, ethnicity, and politics

in Nigeria, there is a noticeable gap concerning localised studies in areas like Ussa LGA. Most studies focus on broader state or national levels, overlooking the unique dynamics at the local government level. Addressing this gap is crucial for developing targeted interventions and policies that consider the specific contexts and challenges of communities like Ussa. (Udoidem & Essien, 2018).

- **Ethno-Religious Conflicts and Political Exploitation**

Ussa LGA, along with neighbouring areas like Takum and Wukari, has experienced persistent ethno-religious tensions. These tensions have often been exacerbated by political actors who exploit ethnic and religious identities for personal or political gain, leading to deep-seated divisions and conflicts within communities. Such exploitation undermines social cohesion and hampers effective governance as opined by Agbo et al. (2021).

- **Youth Marginalization and Socio-Economic Disruption**

The recurring conflicts have had detrimental effects on the youth in Ussa LGA. Disruptions in education due to insecurity, coupled with limited economic opportunities, have led to increased unemployment and social unrest among young people. This marginalization not only affects individual livelihoods but also poses a threat to the region's long-term development as indicated by Agbo et al. (2021)

- **Proliferation of Arms and Rise in Violent Crimes**

The ethno-religious conflicts have contributed to the proliferation of small arms and light weapons in the region. This influx has escalated violent crimes, including armed robbery and communal clashes, further destabilising the area and complicating efforts toward peace and security.

- **Weak Governance and Ineffective Conflict Management**

Weak governance structures and inadequate conflict management mechanisms have often hampered efforts by the Taraba State government to address these conflicts. As averred by Ohazurike (2023) the lack of inclusive political processes and equitable resource distribution has perpetuated feelings of marginalisation among certain groups, fuelling further unrest.

PROSPECTS FOR ADDRESSING THE CHALLENGES

- **Youth Empowerment and Educational Programs**

Investing in youth through education and vocational training can mitigate the allure of participating in conflicts. Empowering young people with skills and opportunities can foster a sense of purpose and reduce their vulnerability to manipulation by divisive political actors Ohazurike (2023).

- **Strengthening Governance and Inclusive Policies**

Implementing inclusive governance practices that ensure equitable representation and resource allocation can address grievances that often lead to conflicts. Strengthening institutions to be more transparent and

accountable can also build trust among diverse communities Madami (2023).

- **Regulation of Arms and Security Reforms**

Establishing stringent measures to control the proliferation of arms and reforming security agencies to be more community-oriented can enhance safety and deter violent activities. Collaborative efforts between the government and local communities are essential in achieving sustainable security Madami (2023).

CONCLUSION

The study of religion and ethnic politics in Ussa Local Government Area reveals the complex and often problematic role of identity in local governance. While religion and ethnicity are central to the cultural and social life of the people, their politicisation has produced significant challenges, including marginalisation, electoral violence, and political exclusion. These issues have not only hindered democratic development in Ussa LGA but have also strained intergroup relations and limited the prospects for inclusive governance.

The research highlights how political actors often exploit religious and ethnic identities for personal or group advantage, further deepening divisions and weakening state institutions. However, the study also identifies opportunities for positive transformation. Through inclusive political practices, interfaith and interethnic dialogue, civic education, and strengthened local institutions, Ussa LGA can move towards a more unified and participatory political environment.

In summary, while the problems of religion and ethnic politics in Ussa are real and persistent, the prospects for reform and coexistence remain promising. What is required is sustained political will, community-level commitment, and scholarly attention to drive forward inclusive and peaceful governance.

- **Recommendations**

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are proposed to address the challenges posed by religion and ethnic politics in Ussa Local Government Area and to enhance peaceful coexistence and inclusive governance:

- c) Government at all levels should ensure that political appointments, electoral processes, and public service opportunities reflect the diverse ethnic and religious composition of Ussa LGA. Equitable representation will help reduce feelings of marginalisation and foster a sense of belonging among all groups.
- d) Traditional institutions, religious bodies, and civil society organisations should collaborate to establish regular dialogue/fora where ethnic and religious leaders can discuss grievances, build trust, and jointly develop strategies for conflict prevention.
- e) The State government should ensure that Civic Education and Public Awareness Campaigns that promote national unity, tolerance, and the value of diversity are targeted to youth, religious followers, and

political actors, emphasising the dangers of divisive identity politics.

- f) Electoral bodies and security agencies should enforce regulations against hate speech, especially during campaign seasons. Political candidates and party officials should be held accountable for inflammatory language that incites ethnic or religious animosity.
- g) The federal government should empower local government through training and resource support to effectively manage diversity and resolve identity-based conflicts. Special units on conflict resolution and inclusion may be established within the council administration.
- h) NGOs, community-based organisations, and donor agencies should invest in grassroots peacebuilding efforts that engage marginalised communities and youth in dialogue, skill development, and community projects that promote shared interests.
- i) Researchers should conduct quality research on the nuances of religion and ethnicity in local politics across Taraba State, using Ussa as a case study. Comparative research can provide broader insights for policy and practice.

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